

Effect of Self-Efficacy and Job Satisfaction on Individual Citizenship Behavior and Its Impact on Professional Commitments

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Research aims: This research study intends to analyze exactly how contextual variables, including self-efficacy and job satisfaction, affect individual citizenship behavior and have an impact on the professional commitment of lecturers at the College of Economics in East Java, Indonesia.

Design/ Approach/ Method : This research study utilizes a quantitative method to discuss the connection between variables. Information from 170 participants was gathered and after that, evaluated with the Architectural Equational Modeling (SEM) method.

Research findings: The results show that Self Efficacy has no critical impact on ICB, and Professional Commitment has an irrelevant effect on ICB, ICB substantially affects Professional Commitment, Self Efficacy has no extensive impact on Professional Commitment, Job Satisfaction significantly affects Professional Commitment and unimportant effect on Professional Commitment.

Theoretical contributions/ Originality: This study extends previous work by investigating the influence of blessed variables in which the results of this study can be input for decision-makers for the development of Private Colleges especially the College of Economics in order to pay more attention to the professional commitment of lecturers in dealing with changes that are so fast and complex in the progress of Information and Communication Technology and globalization.

Practitioner/ Policy implications: This research study offers understanding right into exactly how the impact of self-efficacy and complete task satisfaction on Private Citizenship Habits and Expert Dedication will be the primary emphasis of this research study.

Research limitation: This research study concentrates on the secondary school from business economics in East Java District, Indonesia. For that reason, the generalization from searchings for can be restricted. Future research studies have to consist of task complete satisfaction in a bigger and much more varied example.

Keywords: Self-efficacy, job satisfaction, individual civic behavior, professional commitment.

1. Introduction

The development of the world of education at this time always comes up with new problems in accordance with developments in globalization in the world, so this is related to the quality of learning that produces graduates who are ready and competent in the face of globalization and the industrial revolution 4.0. Currently, one of the critical challenges facing all tertiary institutions is how to manage quality. Especially in the world of education and the global industry. In the industrial world, quality is the value of output, which is the top priority. Moreover, service products (services) quality is the main differentiating factor needed by consumers. Educating the nation is part of Indonesia's current human resource development. Through quality education, people will be knowledgeable, noble, and healthy. Based on this phrase clearly states that through education quality, human resources will be formed

Lecturers in carrying out their duties as educators, professionalism is needed by lecturers with full responsibility and always maintain a conducive academic atmosphere. Lecturers need the availability of infrastructure in learning in the implementation of learning. The problem faced by lecturers today is the rapid development of technology, especially technology that supports the tri dharma of higher education, namely learning, research, and community service. So to develop professional skills and career development of lecturers to improve professionalism will encounter many obstacles. Globalization requires lecturers to develop their abilities in the field of IT-based learning. For that reason, lecturers also need to have the ability to innovate learning more than in their areas.

The job satisfaction of lecturers and the professional commitment of educators become very important in the field of education. This shows that task complete satisfaction and expert dedication are adjoined (Sunardi, 2017). There're precursor elements that have a considerable impact on worker task complete satisfaction, including factors related to work, factors related to work conditions, considerations about coworkers, factors related to supervision, factors related to promotion, and factors related to salary. The lecturers will continue to work in higher education, as well as a high commitment to lecturers. The opposite condition is the low satisfaction with external factors, which causes low performance, loyalty, and opens up opportunities to find other jobs to fulfill the satisfaction.

Previous research conducted on variables related to the effect of Self-Efficacy, Job Satisfaction on Individual Citizenship Behavior and Professional Commitment, researchers found several research results including H. Shamina (2014) who examined the effect from task complete satisfaction on expert dedication in college with the number of respondents was 250 lecturers from the University of Bharathiar Coimbatore. Similar research was also conducted by Debora E. Purba, Janneke K. Oostrom, Henk T. Van der Molen and Marise Ph Birted (2015) on Character and business citizenship habits in Indonesia : The mediating impact from affective dedication of 300 Indonesian cement employees with seven the factory in West Java also Liqayat Bashir (2017) about Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Relation to Professional 300 Punjab teachers in India and Sarah Basu (2016) who researched Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers as many as 98 Bareilly District Middle School teachers. Some research gaps that researchers found from previous research can be used as a reference for research that researchers will do and based on the research gaps, the influence of self-efficacy and job satisfaction on individual Citizenship Behavior and Professional Commitment will be the main focus in this study.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Paradigma theory

Theories and concepts used as a reference to explain the variables to be studied the variables of self-efficacy, job satisfaction, Individual Citizenship Behavior, and Professional Commitment. In the aggregate that the theories and concepts put forward cover these research variables from the perspective of organizational behavior theory. This research is explanatory research in which the focus in this study is how the effect of self-efficacy, and job satisfaction on Individual Citizenship Behavior and Professional Commitment of College Lecturers in Economics in East Java by using the theory of Self-Efficacy (Bandura (1997), where it is a belief on one's ability to do tasks.

People that are positive in their capabilities have the tendency to be successful, whereas those that constantly seem like stop working have the tendency to stop working. Self-efficacy belongs to the expert dedication, where if somebody has high self-efficacy, this has the tendency to be a dedication to what he's doing. People with high self-efficacy will accomplish much better efficiency because these people have powerful inspiration, remove objectives, mentally steady, and their capability to offer the very best efficiency with a dedication to effective tasks or habits. Expert dedication describes the stamina from private recognition with the occupation. People with high expert dedication are defined by having actually high count on and approval in expert objectives, a wish to do their finest for the occupation, and a solid wish to preserve

subscription in the occupation (Mowday et alia., 1979). As one of the important factors in explaining work behavior, Professional Commitment is one of the attractive topics that get a lot of attention from academics and practitioners.

2.2 Grand Theory

Theories and concepts used as a reference to explain the variables to be studied the variables of self-efficacy, job satisfaction, Individual Citizenship Behavior, and Professional Commitment. In the aggregate that the theories and concepts put forward cover these research variables from the perspective of organizational behavior theory. Complete satisfaction or discontentment really felt by people is the outcome from contrasts or spaces made by oneself to different examples that he's acquired from the job and that ends up being his assumptions. The private will really feel pleased if the distinction of space in between the individual's requirements and what is acquired from a little task, or else discontentment will be gotten in touch with by the private if the distinction or inconsistency in between the individual's requirements with what is made from a remarkable task.

Job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are two different things. According to this theory, job characteristics can be grouped into two categories, one called Dissatisfier or hygiene factors, and the other is called satisfier or motivator. The importance of an intelligent understanding of human behavior in determining organizational effectiveness has been felt in the twenty-first century today by every organization, both profit-oriented and non-profit. In today's business world, which is increasingly competitive, demanding that everyone is running a business requires creative and innovative management. Although creative and innovative business management efforts are very important to do to improve organizational performance.

2.3 Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses Development

Based on several literature studies and the results of the empirical studies described above, the conceptual framework can be illustrated in this study as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Based upon the formula from the issue, research study goals, literature review and conceptual framework proposed, the following hypothesis is proposed H1: Self-Efficacy has a significant effect on the Individual Citizenship Behavior of the College of Economics lecturers in East Java, H2: Self-Efficacy has a significant effect on the Professional Commitment of School lecturers College of Economics in East Java, H3: Job Satisfaction has a significant effect on Individual Citizenship Behavior Lecturers at the College of Economics in East Java, H4: Job Satisfaction has a significant effect on the Professional Commitment of College of Economics Lecturers in East Java and H5: Individual Citizenship Behavior influences significantly towards the Professional Commitment of College Lecturers of Economics in East Java.

3. Research Methodology

To operationalize this research construct, operational definitions and actions are developed as follows. Self-efficacy is a lecturer's assessment of the confidence in his own abilities and the belief in the success that is always achieved, which makes him work harder and always produce the best. Measurement of self-efficacy

variables based on indicators of the development of the dimensions according to Bandura, namely the Dimension Magnitude / Level, Generality Dimension and Strength dimensions.

Job Satisfaction is defined as a match between employee expectations and the reality obtained at work. Job satisfaction in this study is the job satisfaction of lecturers on their work as a lecturer in the School of Economics in East Java. The indicator to measure this variable refers to Wexley and Yukl (1977), namely the gap between the difference between what should be and the reality that can be felt, Justice is the level of fairness or injustice obtained in carrying out the task, a supportive work environment, work mentally challenging, namely liking work that provides an opportunity to use the skills, opportunities, and abilities in offering work and promotion, which is carried out on the basis of work performance.

Individual Citizenship Behavior is specified as private habits that are totally free, is not straight or clearly associated with the benefit system, and can improve the efficient performance of the company. There're four signs from ICB industrialized by William and Anderson (1991) Altruism, Courtesy, Peacekeeping, Cheerleading. Commitment to the profession is the involvement of individuals in having identification and values and loyalty to the profession they carry. This variable is measured through five dimensions, which are further detailed in the indicator. The five dimensions referred to are Education and training, Responsibilities, Code of Ethics, Professional Organizations and Life Careers.

The population in this study are lecturers who do not yet have functional functions. According to hair et. (1998), The recommended number of samples for Structural Equation analysis ranges from 100 to 200 or more but should not exceed 400 because the model will be very sensitive. Therefore, the example was taken utilizing the Slovin equation (Umar 2004). The quantity of tests is resolved to utilize the Slovin equation as pursues:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Information:

n = Number of Samples

N = Number of population

e = Percent of allowance for inaccuracy due to sampling errors that can still be tolerated (in this study an estimated 5%)

From these calculations, a total of 170 lecturer samples were obtained. The dimension range is equated right into Indonesian, and back-to-back translations are put on guarantee a high degree from uniformity. Dimension products exist where participants are asked to price their understandings on a 5-point Likert range, varying from 1 (highly disagree) to 5 (highly concur). The analytical tool used is Structural Equational Modeling with the help of AMOS 24.0 Software.

4 Data Analysis and Findings

4.1 Measurement Model Analysis

The construct in the SEM technique is called the latent variable (the variable that cannot be measured directly), and the indicator is the observed variable (the observed variable, as the operationalization of the measurement of the latent variable). After the constructs of the constructs and indicators are stated in the model, then using the SEM procedure, a validity and reliability test is performed. The calculation results show that the value of t (indicated by the value of CR) for loading each indicator is greater than the critical value at the Significance level of 0.05 (Critical value = 1.96) and the probability value is smaller than α (0.05) or loading factor value > 0.5, so it can be concluded that all indicator variables are significantly related to the five constructs that are determined. All indicators can be declared valid. Construct reliability of all variables based on the calculation results, is known to be above the recommended value of 0.7. Thus all indicators for each construct are declared reliable.

4.2 Structural Model Analysis

Screening the design in SEM intends to see the suitability of the design. The outcomes from screening the suitability from the design in this research study exist in Table 1. Based upon the computation outcomes, it's

understood that from the 8 requirements utilized to evaluate whether a design is possible or otherwise, 7 requirements are satisfied, and one limited criterion, therefore the design can be stated to be considerable, which implies that there're a suit in between design and information.

Tabel 1. Goodness of fit test

Criteria	Cut-off value	The calculation results	Remarks
Chi Square	Expected to be small (< χ^2 dengan df = 578 is 628,409) Prob. > 0,05	628,49 Prob.= 0,072	Good
Sig. Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,072	Good
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,023	Good
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,849	Marginal
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,817	Marginal
CMIN/DF	≤ 2 or 3	1,087	Good
TLI	$\geq 0,90$	0,985	Good
NFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,858	Marginal

The following stage is to test the theories created in the model. The path coefficient test results are presented below, and from the corresponding model, each path coefficient can be implemented.

Tabel 2. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Causality relationship			Path coefficient	Standard Error	CR	Probability
H1	ICB	<---	SE	0.312	0.171	1.823	0.068
H2	ICB	<---	JS	0.098	0.061	1.617	0.106
H3	PC	<---	ICB	0.204	0.088	2.323	0.020
H4	PC	<---	SE	0.305	0.169	1.807	0.071
H5	PC	<---	JS	0.112	0.054	2.060	0.039

From the count, results got an examination that Self-Efficacy has no critical impact on Individual Citizenship Behavior in the College of Economics in East Java. The estimation consequences of the Self-Efficacy variable parameters for the Individual Citizenship Behavior show unimportant outcomes, which can be seen from the positive way coefficient of 0.312 with C.R. of 1,823 and got a critical likelihood (p) of 0.068 higher than the degree of Significance (α) expected of 0.05. Proficient Commitment insignificantly affects Individual Citizenship Behavior at the College of Economics in East Java. The estimation aftereffects of the parameters of the Professional Commitment towards Individual Citizenship Behavior demonstrated inconsequential outcomes, which can be seen from the positive way coefficient of 0.098 with C.R. equivalent to 1.617 and a critical likelihood (p) of 0.106 is higher than the degree of Significance (α) expected of 0.05.

Individual Citizenship Behavior has a significant effect on Professional Commitment at the College of Economics in East Java. The estimation results of the parameters of the Individual Citizenship Behavior variable on Professional Commitment show significant results, which can be seen from the positive path coefficient of 0.204 with C.R. of 2,323 and obtained a considerable probability (p) of 0.020 less than the Significance level (α) required of 0.05. Self-Efficacy has no significant effect on Professional Commitment at the College of Economics in East Java. The results of the parameter estimation of the Self-Efficacy variable against Professional Commitment showed insignificant results, which can be seen from the positive way coefficient of 0.305 with C.R. of 1.807 and got a huge likelihood (p) of 0.071 higher than the degree of Significance (α) expected of 0.05. Employment Satisfaction substantially affects Professional Commitment at the College of Economics in East Java. The aftereffects of the estimation of the variable parameters Job Satisfaction towards Professional Commitment indicated critical outcomes, which can be seen from the negative

way coefficient of 0.112 with C.R. of 2.060 and got an extensive likelihood (p) of 0.039 littler than the degree of Significance (α) expected of 0.05.

4.3 Indirect Effect

Path analysis is used to assess the direct and indirect effects between exogenous and endogenous variables through intervening variables. The calculation results from the report are as follows:

Table 3. Path coefficient

Variable	Path coefficient		Effect	
	PC	ICB	Indirect effect	Total
SE	0.267	0.260	0.057	0.324
JS	0.256	0.214	0.055	0.311
ICB	0.214	0.000	0.000	0.214

From the calculation results, obtained analysis is known that the direct effect given self-efficacy on the professional commitment of 0.267. While the indirect effect of self-efficacy through the Individual Citizenship Behavior on professional commitment is the multiplication between the beta value of the self-efficacy variable against the Individual Citizenship Behavior with the Individual Citizenship Behavior beta value of professional commitment Namely: $0.260 \times 0.214 = 0.056$. Then the total effect given self-efficacy on professional commitment is the direct effect coupled with the indirect effect, namely: $0.260 + 0.057 = 0.323$. Based on the calculation above, it is known that the value of direct influence is 0.267 and the indirect effect is 0.056, which means that the value of indirect effect is smaller than the value of direct influence, this result shows job satisfaction that indirectly Self-Efficacy through Individual Citizenship Behavior has an indirect effect significant to professional commitment.

The direct effect of job satisfaction on professional commitment is 0.256. While the indirect effect of job satisfaction through Individual Citizenship Behavior on professional commitment is the multiplication of the beta value of job satisfaction on Individual Citizenship Behavior with the Individual Citizenship Behavior beta value on professional commitment, $0.256 \times 0.214 = 0.046$. Then the total effect given by job satisfaction on professional commitment is the straight impact combined with the indirect impact, specifically : $0.256 + 0.046 = 0.302$. Based upon the over computation outcomes acquired the worth from the straight impact from 0.256 and indirect impact from 0.046 Which implies that the worth from indirect impact is smaller sized compared to the worth from straight impact, these results indicate job satisfaction that indirectly jobs satisfaction through Individual Citizenship Behavior has an indirect effect significant to professional commitment.

5 Discussion

Self-efficacy has a positive and not significant effect on Individual Citizenship Behavior. This shows job satisfaction that positive self-efficacy possessed by lecturers cannot contribute to higher education. Based on the value of the biggest loading factor, self-efficacy is characterized by lecturers' confidence in their abilities related to IT development in the learning model when there is SPADA namely the online learning system held by the government requires lecturers to innovate in learning especially with the use of ICT (Information Communication Technology). Lecturers of the College of Economics like assignments even though the task is difficult, which shows job satisfaction that lecturers must complete their IT-based assignments even though the lecturer concerned is an economics lecturer. This indicates that the better the self-efficacy of lecturers who are appointed to job satisfaction with the nature of Strength, the lecturer believes in his ability to prove that a lecturer is always trying new things, thinking open to new ideas or thoughts and easily adapting to new situations or circumstances, this is very following the task of a lecturer who must update or update a lot of

problems that occur, especially those related to materials and materials as well as the development or progress of science and technology because it is the duty of lecturers to provide up-to-date knowledge to students, it will be increasing it is likely to do a good job even exceeding what should be done or exceeding the obligations imposed by universities.

Self-efficacy has a positive and not significant effect on professional commitment. This shows job satisfaction that the positive self-efficacy of the lecturer cannot contribute to the lecturer professional. Based on the value of the biggest loading factor, self-efficacy is characterized by lecturers' confidence in their abilities related to IT development in the learning model when there is SPADA namely the online learning system held by the government requires lecturers to innovate in learning especially with the use of Information Communication Technology. Lecturers of the College of Economics like assignments even though the task is difficult, which shows job satisfaction that lecturers must complete their IT-based assignments even though the lecturer concerned is an economics lecturer. This indicates that the better the self-efficacy of lecturers who are appointed to job satisfaction with the nature of Strength, the lecturer believes in his ability to prove that a lecturer is always trying new things, thinking open to new ideas or thoughts and easily adapting to new situations or circumstances, this is very in accordance with the task of a lecturer who must update or update a lot of problems that occur, especially those related to materials and materials as well as the development or progress of science and technology because it is the duty of lecturers to provide up-to-date knowledge to students, it will be increasing it is likely to do a good job even exceeding what should be done or exceeding the obligations imposed by universities.

Job satisfaction has a positive and not significant effect on Individual Citizenship Behavior. This shows job satisfaction that lecturers who feel job satisfaction will not be compelled to show the behavior. Based on the loading factor of the job satisfaction variable with the Gap indicator. From the results of the description of the variable job satisfaction with a gap indicating job satisfaction answers from respondents agreed by 27%. This indicates that the lecturer earns income as a lecturer profession, not in accordance with his expectations. Higher education provides salary based on merit pay, which is getting a salary based on performance, so if the lecturer actively conducts tri dharma of higher education, he will get income according to his expectations. This makes many lecturers who do not do Individual Citizenship Behavior is a lecturer will find it challenging to do work that exceeds the demands of the tertiary institution. Lecturers must apply knowledge, abilities, and skills for the advancement of higher education. Meanwhile, in terms of age, the dominant respondents aged 46-55 years and older indicate wisdom in carrying out and enforcing work on academic rules and relationships or relationships with fellow lecturers, superiors, and students. Perfect maturity in optimizing the opportunities available in developing themselves and the moral responsibilities that are carried out in carrying out the profession as a lecturer.

This finding supports the results of previous studies conducted by this study, pointing to job satisfaction as a weak effect between job satisfaction with OCB. Dickinson (2009) concluded that there was no influence between job satisfaction with OCB. Dickinson (2009) conducted a study to examine how some employee attitudes affect job satisfaction, relationships with superiors, perceptions of fairness received, organizational commitment, job stress, the stress outside of work, affect extra-role behavior, or OCB. The consequences of the examination (Herminingsih, 2012) demonstrate work fulfillment that activity fulfillment has no critical impact on OCB, implying that it doesn't bolster the exploration depicted in the past area of this investigation. In any case, this examination created indistinguishable discoveries from Intaraprasong et al. (2012), which brought about the securing that position fulfillment has a delicate association with the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of representatives at one of the University emergency clinics in Thailand. The constructive outcome of occupation fulfillment on Individual Citizenship Behavior got generous help through this investigation. This is in accordance with a look into delivered by Foote and Tang (2008), who found that OCB was decidedly impacted by work fulfillment. The consequence of the exploration was substantially influenced by Organizational Commitment toward OCBs, Job Satisfaction, Personality, and Professionalism just noteworthy impact on OCB-O, Sambung (2012).

Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on Professional Commitment, and this shows job satisfaction that positive job satisfaction possessed by lecturers can contribute to higher education. This finding supports the results of previous studies conducted by this study, pointing to job satisfaction and the effect between job satisfaction and professional commitment. Liqayat Bashir (2017); Sarah Basu (2016); Shamima (2014); Yang et., al (2012); Emami (2012). There is a significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and professional commitment. This proves that job satisfaction and professional commitment are significantly interrelated. These findings support the results of previous studies conducted by this study, pointing to job satisfaction effects between Individual Citizenship Behavior with professional commitment. Purba et., al (2015); Özdem (2012); Rika (2017); Bogler (2004), a positive and significant relationship between professional commitment and Individual Citizenship Behavior.

6 Conclusion

Based on previous studies and discussions, this can be wrapped up that self-efficacy belongs to the expert dedication, where if somebody has high self-efficacy, this has the tendency to be a dedication to what he's doing. Bandura (1997) exposed that people with high self-efficacy would accomplish much better efficiency because these people have powerful inspiration, remove objectives, are mentally steady, and have the capability to offer the very best efficiency. Success in self-leadership depends on the ability to coordinate intentions, thoughts, and actions. With the right support, individuals can monitor and control their own behavior (Robbins, 2006). It can be concluded that one of the elements or factors that can increase commitment to the profession is self-leadership. Therefore, if a lecturer applies self-leadership to himself well and maximally, then it will have a positive effect and is directly proportional to professional commitment.

There are two factors that affect commitment to the profession, namely internal factors and external factors. Internal factors are more directed at teachers themselves, both individually and as institutions, as a profession that demands greater awareness and responsibility in carrying out their roles and functions as educators. External factors in this context are more related to how government policies encourage policy and atmosphere that can stimulate and produce professional lecturers. In order to increase the commitment of the professors' professions, lecturer competencies are needed on yearly or semi-annual job records as a method to screen, empower, and enhance lecturer self-confidence.

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